

Battle of the Sexes? Perceptions and Interpretations of Gender Roles in North Cyprus.

By Feriha Dikmen¹

Girne American University, Cyprus (Northern)

Abstract

This study sets out to map the perceptions and interpretation of gender roles by Turkish Cypriots living in the Northern part of the island. The study uses a Content Analytic approach to analyze advertisements generated and used by the BEKO company in 2012 with the aim of both understanding the embedded gender cues used and the perception and interpretation of such cues by the study participants. Findings reveal that while content analysis of the advertisements contain promotory messages, they also carry subtle gender related messages which re-affirm the society's accepted posture towards the role of men and women. Hence reinforcing societal stereotypes regarding gender. Also, participant responses revealed that females perceived and interpreted the contents of the adverts under study from a gender representation perspective, while males reflected a gender role perspective.

Key words: *tv adverts, gender representation, gender roles, cultivation of ideas, consumerism*

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Introduction

Advertisement is one of the most influential ways of shaping cultural norms and values. This type of communication media creates messages and scenarios which are recognizable and socially acceptable by the audiences. Moreover, these systems and structures of communication, that influence social reality and reinforce the concepts of socially acceptable behavior as well as image, affect the process of social change. In this context, data generated from this research carries a significant value in that it provides the bases for the development of Northern Cypriot media and advertising in general through facilitating the formulation of culturally-indexed strategies; thus supporting the improvement of gender-sensitivity within the society.

In order to examine and better understand this phenomenon, the following research questions were posed (a) Does gender representation in Turkish television adverts effect consumer behaviour of Northern Cyprus viewers? (b) Is there a gender-specific difference in the effects of

gender representation in Turkish television adverts on consumer behaviour of North Cyprus viewers?. After a review of extant literature and related theories, the following research hypothesis was posed as a possible finding to be expected upon completion of the study: **H₁**: The profile of current viewer (Northern Cypriot) perception of gender representation in television advertisements reflects a gender-sensitive society”.

The Coding System

In order to better analyse the advertisements under study from a content analytic procedure, key words related to the focus of research were identified and coded. Synonymous words reflecting to the some discourse were grouped under these codings. The formulation of these codings is indicated in table 4.1.

Table 1: Coding for Gender Representation and 2012 BEKO Advertisements

CODES GENERAL THEME	RELEVANT WORDS
1. MASCULINITY	Provider, Men, Father, Husband, Matcho, Businessman, Strenth
2. FEMININITY	Women, Housewife, Female, Mother, Beauty, Wife, Passive, BusinessWomen
3. SOCIETY CHANGE	Culture, Community, Old generation, Difference, New generation, Change, Social, Technology
4. REPRESENTATION	Image, Belief, Only, Attractiveness, Representation Reflect, Shaping
5. ROLES	Gender roles, Men’s roles, Women’s Roles, Head/Leader/Authority
6. IDENTITY	Family, Formation, Independent, Development, Gender Identity
7. CONSUMERISM	Buying/Purchasing, Influence, Biased, One-directional, Effect, Advertising, Branding, Trust

8. SEX	Sexuality, Sex
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Content Analysis

Content analysis is a research method used in many areas of media. It is intensively relied on especially in recent academic and sector specific researches in television media. Weber (1990) defines content analysis is a systematic, replicable technique by narrowing words into fewer categories based on explicit rules of coding. Holsti (1969) describes content analysis as; any sort of technique to find out the conclusion by objective and systematic way by identifying specified characteristics of messages. As Holsti’s defined it is not limited to domain of textual analysis in the techniques of content analysis, can be applied in different areas such as coding student drawings, or coding of actions observed in videotaped studies.

Behind the reliance on coding and categorizing data which is making content analysis rich and expressive, it is a result of simple counting words. Categorizing can be summarized as; "A group of words with similar meaning or connotations" (Weber, 1990, p. 37).

In this study individual responses were analysed for the coding and the frequency of the use of these codes were tabulated for each interview questions and the means were compared.

Results of Content Analysis

Results of the analysis of individual responses using the codes listed Table 2 are summarized in the following tables in parallel with general profile followed by question sequence.

Table 2: General code frequency in responses to all Questions

Frequency of use	CODES							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8

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Mean and SD	1.3±1.6	2.4±2.1	1.2±1.4	0.9±1.1	0.5±0.9	1±1.8	4±4	0±0
	0.4±0.8	1±1.5	0.8±1.2	0.2±0.4	0.03±0.1	0.2±0.7	6±2.7	0±0
	2.9±1.8	4±2.2	1.8±1.6	1.5±1.2	1.2±1.3	1.05±1.3	2.7±1.6	2.5±1.5
	2.3±2	3.2±2.3	1.7±1.4	2.1±1.3	2.7±1.8	1.1±1	2.9±1.8	1.3±1.2
Total Mean and SD	1.7±1.6	2.7±2	1.4±1.4	1.2±1	1.1±1	0.8±1.2	4±2.5	0.9±0.7

In table above shows the general code frequencies in responses to all questions. The most frequently used code is 7, whereas the least frequently used code is 8 and the rest shows variations (2, 1, 3, 4, 5, 6).

Table 3: Code frequency in responses to Question 1 (Mean ± SD)

Groups	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
General N=80	1.3±1.6	2.4±2.1	1.2±1.4	0.9±1.1	0.5±0.9	1±1.8	4±4	0±0
AgeGroups								
18-25 N=40	0.2±0.5	0.9±1.3	0.8±1.3	0.3±0.6	0.3±0.7	0.8±0.9	3.7±1.5	0±0
40 and +N=40	2.4±1.6	3.9±1.6	1.7±1.4	1.4±1.2	0.8±1	1.2±1.4	4±0	0±0
GenderGroups								
Female N=40	1.7±1.8	2.7±1.9	1.4±1.4	0.9±1	0.5±1	1.1±1.2	4±0	0±0
Male N=40	0.9±1.3	2.1±2.2	1.1±1.4	0.8±1.3	0.5±1	1±1.2	4±0	0±0

Question 1 : What is your general opinion about the adverts you have watched?

The analysis of the general responses to Question 1 shows the highest frequency of use of code 7 (consumerism). In contrast, the lowest frequency of use is for code 8 (sex). When the responses were analysed according to age group 1 (18-25), the highest frequency of use was observed with code 7 (consumerism) whereas the lowest frequency of use was with code 8 (sex). The responses of age group 2 (40 and above) indicate the highest frequency of use of the code 2 (femininity) and the lowest frequency of use of the code 8 (sex). The analysis of the responses of the female participants show the highest frequency of use of the code 2 (femininity). Whereas lowest frequency of use was of code 8 (sex). The analysis of the responses of the male participants show the highest frequency of use of the code 2 (femininity). On the otherhand the lowest frequency of use was observed with code 8 (sex).

Table 4: Code frequency ranking for Question 1

	CODES							
General	7	2	1	6	3	4	5	8
18-25	7	2	3	6	5	4	1	8
40+	2	7/1	3	4/6	5			8
Female	2	7	1	3	6	4	5	8
Male	2	7	3	6/1	4	5		8

When the ranking of code frequencies are analyzed the general profile shows the following ranking: 7, 2, 1, 6, 3, 4, 5, 8. 18-25 age group shows a somewhat similar profile to that of the general profile, particularly the first two positions and the rest shows variations (3, 6, 5, 4, 1, 8). In contrast 40 and above age group as well as the gender groups shows similarity in themselves ranking code 2 in the first positions and code 7 in the second positions. The rest of the codes show variability. One common element in the ranking profile is positioning of code 8 in the last place.

Table 5: Code frequency in responses to Question 2 (Mean ± SD)

Groups	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
General N=80	0.4±0.8	1±1.5	0.8±1.2	0.2±0.4	0.03±0.1	0.2±0.7	6±2.7	0±0
AgeGroups								

18-25 N=40	0.4±1	0.9±1.5	0.9±1.3	0.08±0.3	0±0	0.2±0.7	7±2.7	0±0
40 and +N=40	0.3±0.7	1.2±1.5	0.7±1.2	0.2±0.5	0.05±0.2	0.2±0.7	2±5	0±0
GenderGroups								
Female N=40	0.6±1	1.2±1.5	1.1±1.4	0.2±0.5	0.03±0.2	0.2±0.7	7±3.1	0±0
Male N=40	0.2±0.4	1±1.5	0.05±0.9	0.08±0.4	0.03±0.2	0.2±1.2	4±0	0±0

Question 2: Do these adverts change your habits of purchasing? Why?

The analysis of the general responses to Question 2 shows the highest frequency of use of code 7 (consumerism). In contrast the lowest frequency of use code 8 (sex). When the responses were analysed according to age group 1 (18-25), the highest frequency of use was observed with code 7 (consumerism) whereas the lowest frequency of use was with code 8 (sex). The responses of age group 2 (40 and above) indicate the highest frequency of use of the code 7 (consumerism) and the lowest frequency of use of the code 8 (sex). The analysis of the responses of the female participants show the highest frequency of use of the code 7 (consumerism). Whereas lowest frequency of use was of code 8 (sex). The analysis of the responses of the male participants show the highest frequency of use of the code 7 (consumerism). On the otherhand the lowest frequency of use was observed with code 8 (sex).

Table 6: Code frequency ranking for Question 2

	CODES							
General	7	2	3	1	5	6	4	8
18-25	7	2	3	1	6	4		5/8
40+	7	2	3	1	6	4	5	8
Female	7	2	3	1	6	4	5	8
Male	7	2	6	3	1	4	5	8

When the ranking of code frequencies are analyzed the general profile shows the following ranking: 7, 2, 3, 1, 5, 6, 4, 8. 18-25 age group shows a somewhat similar profile particularly the first four positions and the rest shows variations (6, 4, 5/8). In contrast 40 and above age group

aswell as the female groups shows similarity in themselves ranking code 2 in first positions and code 7 in the second positions, code 3 in the third positions, code 1 in the fourth positions, code 6 in the fifth positions, code 4 in the sixth positions, code 5 in the seventh positions and the code 8 in the last positions. On the other hand, when we analyzed the male groups, 40 and above age group aswell as the female groups shows similarity in themselves ranking code 2 in first positions and code 7 in the second positions and the rest show variations (6, 3, 1, 4, 5, 8). The rest of the codes shows variability. One common element in the ranking profile is the positioning of code 8 in the last place.

Table 7: Code frequency in responses to Question 3 (Mean ± SD)

Groups	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
General N=80	2.9±1.8	4±2.2	1.8±1.6	1.5±1.2	1.2±1.3	1.05±1.3	2.7±1.6	2.5±1.5
AgeGroups								
18-25 N=40	0.4±1	0.9±1.5	0.9±1.3	0.08±0.3	0±0	0.2±0.7	7±2.7	0±0
40 and +N=40	2.3±1.6	3.2±1.7	1.2±1.3	0.9±1.2	0.7±0.9	0.5±0.9	2.3±1.6	2.5±1.4
GenderGroups								
Female N=40	3.4±1.6	4.8±2.5	2.1±1.8	1.5±1.2	1.7±1.5	1.4±1.8	2.9±1.7	3.1±1.5
Male N=40	2.4±1.9	3.2±1.7	1.5±1.3	1.4±1.2	0.7±0.9	0.8±1	2.5±1.4	2±1.3

Question 3: What would you say related to gender in the adverts you have watched?

The analysis of the general responses to Question 3 shows the highest frequency of use of code 2 (femininity). In contrast the lowest frequency of use code 6 (identity). When the responses were analysed according to age group 1 (18-25), the highest frequency of use was observed with code 7 (consumerism) whereas the lowest frequency of use was with codes 8 and 5 (sex and roles). The responses of age group 2 (40 and above) indicate the highest frequency of use of the code 2 (femininity) and the lowest frequency of use of the code 6 (identity). The analysis of the responses of the female participants show the highest frequency of use of the code 2 (femininity). Whereas lowest frequency of use was of code 4 (representation). The analysis of the responses

18-25	1.8±2	3±2.2	1.7±1.5	2.3±1.3	3.2±2.1	1.8±1.2	3.1±1.7	1.5±1.3
40 and above	2.8±2	3.4±2.4	1.4±1.2	1.9±1.2	2.1±1.3	1.1±0.9	2.7±1.8	1.1±1.1
GenderGroups								
Female	2.9±1.8	4.3±2.2	1.8±1.5	2.4±1.5	3±2	1.5±1.1	3.1±1.7	1.7±1.3
Male	1.8±2.1	2.2±1.9	1.4±1.2	1.7±1	2.4±1.7	0.8±0.9	2.7±1.8	1±1

Question 4: In the adverts you have watched how much role do you think these adverts play in the identification of gender roles?

The analysis of the general responses to Question 4 shows the highest frequency of use of code 2 (femininity). In contrast the lowest frequency of use code 6 (identity). When the responses were analysed according to age group 1 (18-25), the highest frequency of use was observed with code 5 (roles) whereas the lowest frequency of use was with code 8 (sex). The responses of age group 2 (40 and above) indicate the highest frequency of use of the code 2 (femininity) and the lowest frequency of use of the code 6 (identity). The analysis of the responses of the female participants show the highest frequency of use of the code 2 (femininity). Whereas lowest frequency of use was of code 6 (identity). The analysis of the responses of the male participants show the highest frequency of use of the code 7 (consumerism). On the otherhand the lowest frequency of use was observed with code 6 (identity).

Table 10: Code frequency ranking for Question 4

	CODES							
General	2	7	5	1	4	3	8	6
18-25	5	2	7	1	4	3	6	8
40 +	2	1	7	5	4	3	8	6
Female	2	5	7	1	4	3	8	6
Male	7	2/5		1	4	3	8	6

When the ranking of code frequencies are analyzed the general profile shows the following ranking: 2, 7, 5, 1, 4, 3, 8, 6. 18-25 age group shows a somewhat similar profile particularly at the last five positions and the rest shows variations (5, 2, 7). In contrast 40 and above age group profile shows the following ranking: 2, 1, 7, 5, 4, 3, 8, 6. Gender group profile shows a somewhat similar profile particularly at the last five positions and the rest shows variations for female profile (2, 5, 7) and for male profile (7, 2/5). The rest of the codes shows variability one common element in the ranking profile positioning of code 6 in the last place apart from 18-25 age group profile.

Discussion

Using the Content analytic approach, when we look at the results reflected on the findings of this study, the television advertisements not only have the functions of informing the consumer, changing their attitudes, convincing them, making a product standing out its competitors by adding value and contributing on the other objectives of organization but also the function of being effective on social gender identity. As a result, the advertisements do not only have functions and aims such as promoting the product and services, but also informing the consumer, ensuring that the consumer does not forget product/service, increasing the demand, realizing the sales, ensuring that the product/service is one step ahead from its competitors, eliminating the lack of communication. Today, many individuals, even involuntarily, do not deliver only the messages that serve to main functions and aims of advertisement due to their television exposure. The cultural values accepted by the society are also included in these messages. Although it is regarded that main messages are created, it is possible to see some indicators that reflect, indicate and remind some behaviors, rights, roles and responsibilities attributed to woman and man by the society among these messages in BEKO 2012 advertisements as well. It is required to be taken into consideration that that such messages including concepts and characteristics on social gender may affect the characters of individuals and especially children, and thus the messages should be prepared by regarding that the messages might cause an affect that may not be anticipated. From the perspective of gender perception in these advertisements, the differences between the perceptions of woman and man viewers are observed. Although no difference is observed between man and woman viewers in general perception after conducting content analysis, when we look at in detail, the perception of woman viewers are towards 'representation' while the perception of man viewers are identified as 'role' in parallel with the traditional social gender roles and stereotypes. These findings answer the fifth subsidiary question of this study.

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